

Notes

Low Frequency Infrared Spectra of some Carbonyl Complexes of Rhodium(I)

MONO M. SINGH^a and DIPAK K. DUTTA*^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Merrimack College, N Andover, MA 01845, U S.A.

^bInorganic Chemistry Division, Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat-785 006

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Infrared carbonyl stretching frequencies have been extensively used as the diagnostic tool for elucidating the structure of carbonyl complexes of transition metals. Other vibrational modes such as carbon-metal-carbon deformation (for dicarbonyls), metal-carbonyl deformation, δ_{M-C-O} and metal-carbon stretching frequencies, ν_{M-C} occurring below 700 cm^{-1} can also provide additional informations about the structural features of these compounds. However, this ir region¹⁻⁶ for these compounds has not been much studied. Browing *et al.*⁷ reported data on skeletal vibrations of different carbonyl complexes including for the compounds $[MX_2(CO)_2]^-$, where $M = \text{Rh}^I, \text{Ir}^I$; $X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-$. We report herein the ir data in the region 700–300 cm^{-1} for some carbonyl complexes of rhodium(I) of the types $[\text{Rh}(\text{N}-\text{N})(\text{CO})_2]\text{BF}_4$, $[\text{Rh}(\text{N}-\text{N})(\text{CO})_2][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]$ and *trans*- $[\text{RhX}(\text{CO})(\text{R}_2\text{S}/\text{R}_2\text{SO})_2]$, where $\text{N}-\text{N} = 2,9$ -dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline (Me_2phen), 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline ($\text{NO}_2\text{-phen}$), 2,2'-biquinoline (*biq*); $\text{R}_2\text{S} =$ dimethyl, di-*n*-propyl sulphide; $\text{R}_2\text{SO} =$ dimethyl, di-*n*-propyl and di-*n*-butyl sulphoxide; $X = \text{Cl}^-$ and Br^- .

Results and Discussion

The ir data of the complexes of rhodium(I) in the region 700–300 cm^{-1} are given in the Table 1. We have selected the deformation modes for our discussion because they are easily identifiable and occur in the region comparatively free from other ligand vibrations. It may be noted that in *cis*- $[\text{RhX}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$ ($X = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-$) having C_{2v} symmetry, two types of vibrations⁷, namely $\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O}$ in-plane, $\delta_{(\text{M}-\text{C}-\text{O})_h}$ and out-of-plane, $\delta_{(\text{M}-\text{C}-\text{O})_v}$ bending and ν_{M-C} stretching vibrations (symmetric and antisymmetric) are ir active. Thus, four bands are expected for such complexes in the region 650–400 cm^{-1} and their occurrence should follow the order¹:

$$\delta_{(\text{M}-\text{C}-\text{O})_v} > \nu_{(\text{M}-\text{C})_{\text{sym}}} > \delta_{(\text{M}-\text{C}-\text{O})_h} > \nu_{(\text{M}-\text{C})_{\text{asym}}}$$

The bands are easily identifiable. Generally, the higher energy bands are of high intensity. Moreover, though some coupling between $\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O}$ deformation and $\text{Rh}-\text{C}$ stretching modes are expected⁸, it is not difficult to assign the bands to a given set of vibrations. Thus, in the spectra of di-

TABLE 1—LOW-FREQUENCY IR BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF Rh^I -CARBONYL COMPLEXES

Compd.	$\delta(\text{RhCO})_v$	$\nu(\text{RhC})_{\text{sym}}$	$\delta(\text{RhCO})_h$	$\nu(\text{RhC})_{\text{asym}}$	$\nu(\text{RhX})$ and other bands
$[\text{Rh}(\text{Me}_2\text{phen})(\text{CO})_2]\text{BF}_4$	610s	502m	485vw	460vw	522 ^a
$[\text{Rh}(\text{NO}_2\text{phen})(\text{CO})_2]\text{BF}_4$	600s	555vw	500vw	460vw	520 ^a
$[\text{Rh}(\text{Me}_2\text{phen})(\text{CO})_2][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]$	610s	505s	490s	456vw	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{NO}_2\text{phen})(\text{CO})_2][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]$	605s 602s	525s	480s	465m	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{biq})(\text{CO})_2][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]$	610s 575w	500w	480s	—	—
$[\text{N}(\textit{n}-\text{pr})_4][\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]^b$	622vs 598wsh	492vs	517m 496w	464w	—
$[\text{N}(\textit{n}-\text{pr})_4][\text{RhBr}_2(\text{CO})_2]^b$	609vs 584sh	487vs	514m 496vs	449m	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{SOX})(\text{CO})_2]^c$	590s	510w	475sh	470m	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{BOX})(\text{CO})_2]^c$	615s 598m	520sh 510m	—	420w	—
$[\text{Rh}(\text{acac})(\text{CO})_2]^c$	620s	500s	495sh 485w	458m	—
$[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})_2]$	554s (2 020) ^e	508m	480m	—	425s ^d
$[\text{RhCl}(\text{CO})(\textit{n}-\text{Pr}_2\text{SO})_2]$	560s (2 020) ^e	520s	504s	445m	410m ^d 320m

(Contd.)

			Table—1 (Contd.)		
[RhBr(CO)(<i>n</i> -Pr ₂ SO) ₂]	548s (2 023) ^e	502m	496s	—	420m ^d
[RhCl(CO)(<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	560s (2 020) ^e	515m	490m	450m	410m ^d 380s 305m 410s ^d
[RhBr(CO)(<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SO) ₂]	550s (2 022) ^e	510s	480s	460m	303
[RhCl(CO)(PMe ₃) ₂] ^f	574vs (1 952) ^e	556m	498m	—	—
[RhBr(CO)(PMe ₃) ₂] ^f	566vs (1 961) ^e	550w	486m	—	—
[RhCl(CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	572s (1 972) ^e	542s	490m	—	425s ^d
[RhBr(CO)(Me ₂ S) ₂]	560s (1 974) ^e	535w	470w	—	425s ^d
[RhCl(CO)(<i>i</i> -Pr ₂ S) ₂]	575s (1 950) ^e	536m	500w	425vw	425s ^d
[RhBr(CO)(<i>i</i> -Pr ₂ S) ₂]	570s (1 951) ^e	530m	—	—	290s 426s ^d

^a ν_{δ} of BF₄⁻. ^bRef. 7. ^cRef. 10. ^d $\nu_{\text{Rh-S}}$. ^e ν_{CO} . ^fPersonal communication from Dr. J. Browning, The University of Bristol.

carbonyl complexes, [Rh(N-N)(CO)₂]⁺ and [Rh(LL)(CO)₂], where N-N=Me₂phen, NO₂-phen etc., LL=singly charged bidentate anionic ligands⁸, the location of Rh-C-O deformation can be ascertained fairly accurately. In case of hexacarbonyl of chromium and molybdenum and pentacarbonyl of iron, the M-C-O deformations⁹⁻¹¹ bands lie above 480 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_{\text{M-C}}$ stretching frequencies occur below 480 cm⁻¹ and upto 340 cm⁻¹.

We have assigned the bands to Rh-C-O deformation modes (Table 1) on the basis of following considerations : (i) if for dicarbonyls, the Rh(CO)₂ fragment is assumed to possess local C_{2v} symmetry, this should give rise to a maximum of four vibrations with at least one having weak intensity⁴ and (ii) in case of monocarbonyl derivatives, the linear Rh-C-O fragment should show two deformation vibrations^{2,3} (out-of-plane occurring at higher frequency range and in-plane occurring at a lower frequency range) and two Rh-C stretching (symmetric and antisymmetric) bands. It may be pointed out that the assignments of M-C-O deformation modes in [RhX(CO)(PR₃)₂] becomes difficult because of the presence of bands due to vibrations of phosphine groups. However, in case of complexes containing R₂S and R₂SO these assignments become straight forward. Table 1 shows that the $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands occur for dicarbonyl and monocarbonyl complexes in the ranges 575-622 and 548-575 cm⁻¹ respectively. The value of $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands is dependent on the amount of $d_{\pi-p_{\pi}}$ bonding between metal and carbonyl group and also upon electron donation of the type $\pi_{\nu}(\text{CO}) \rightarrow \text{Vacant } p_z(\text{Rh})$ ^{4,12}. It is interesting to note that in monocarbonyl complexes, the $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands are found to shift to lower energy^{4,13} in the bromo derivative compared to chloro complexes, but a reverse trend is observed for ν_{CO} bands in the corresponding complexes¹⁴. This can be explained by the fact that Br⁻ is stronger π -acceptor than Cl⁻ and competes more strongly with CO group for d_{π} -electrons of rhodium(I) which in turn decreases

the degree of interaction of Rh(d_{π} filled) \rightarrow CO (vacant π^*). This interaction weakens the bonding Rh-C and results in lower $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ and higher bond order of CO and consequently higher ν_{CO} bands. It is evident from the Table 1 that in square-planar complexes, [RhX(CO)L₂], X=Cl⁻, Br⁻; L=R₂S, R₂SO, the magnitude of shift of ν_{CO} from chloro to bromo derivative is much lower compared to the corresponding shifts of $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ bands. This shows that the change of halide ion in the complexes has greater impact on $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ band

Fig. 1. A general relationship between $\delta_{(\text{Rh-C-O})\nu}$ and ν_{CO} bands.

compared to ν_{CO} bands. On the other hand, in passing from the complexes containing R_2SO to those R_2S , a greater shift (about $50-70\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of ν_{CO} bands compared to the corresponding shift (about $15-25\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of $\delta_{(\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O})\nu}$ bands is observed. Thus, it reflects clearly the effect of change of ligands on $\delta_{(\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O})\nu}$ and ν_{CO} bands. A simple relationship between $\delta_{(\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O})\nu}$ and ν_{CO} for the monocarbonyl complexes is shown in Fig. 1.

Experimental

All the compounds were prepared according to the reported methods¹⁴. Hydrated rhodium trichloride (Johnson Mathey), analytically pure Me_2Phen , $\text{NO}_2\text{-Phen}$, biq (E. Merck), all sulphoxides and sulphides (Aldrich) were used without further purification. The solvents were purified by standard methods. Elemental analysis were done at C.S.I.R.O., Australia.

Ir spectra (nujol/CsI) were recorded on Specord 75 IR and Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometers.

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